

STAFF GUIDE TO SETTING UP THE SVM SURVEY

Platform:

The originator of the Student Voice Toolkit used Microsoft Forms to garner student comments for SVM purposes. Other platforms are of course available. It is recommended that you use a platform which:

- enables you to generate a QR code for use in class, so students do not need to log in to the platform to provide feedback, thus removing a barrier to the provision of feedback; and
- allows quick and easy downloading of the data into an editable excel spreadsheet (this spreadsheet will become the Feedback & Comments document).

There is easily accessible guidance on <https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/forms> on both creating and sharing a survey, as well as extracting data from a completed survey into a spreadsheet.

Suggested Questions:

The questions posed are up to you. It is useful to pose the following question to enable you to track themes across cohorts: **What year are you in? [first, second, etc]**

For your remaining questions, try to ensure that they are open and include an opportunity for students to report on positives, not just on perceived issues. It is recommended that the same question bank is used for SVM 1, 2 and 3 (with the addition of two extra questions for SVM 3: see below).

Note: Following ethically approved research undertaken by the author with staff and students, the Framework is predicated on module issues sitting outside of the SVM process, so module-related questions do not appear in this SVM survey bank. Pilots of long and short surveys, and closed- and open-questions, during 2017-18 and 2018-19 revealed that the method most likely to garner valuable feedback is the inclusion of **as few questions as possible**, but with the opportunity to provide as much rich qualitative data as possible. It is therefore recommended that all questions (save for 'What year are you in?' above) are free-text and non-compulsory, so that those who only wish to comment on one area can do so without having to respond to what they may perceive as superfluous questions.

The questions you include in your SVM survey might include the following:

- Please let us know what you think about the **Library** provision? Please tell us about positives, as well as any suggestions for improvement you may have.
- Please let us know what you think about the **Careers Service** provision? Please tell us about positives, as well as any suggestions for improvement you may have.
- Please let us know what you think of the support you have been provided with by your **personal tutor** so far this year. Please tell us about positives, as well as any suggestions for improvement you may have.

It may also be useful to ask:

- Any other comments [this could alternatively be titled 'Departmental comments']: please use this space to tell us about anything not covered by the questions above (note to students - this is not the space to comment on one module directly – this is for module review – but do mention themes that cut across modules e.g. timetabling)

Additional Recommended Questions for SVM 3:

For SVM 3, at the end of the year, it is recommended that in addition to asking the questions you asked for SVM 1 and 2, you ask the additional following questions:

- If you have raised issues during this academic year via the Student Voice Meeting process, do you feel your query has been answered? YES/NO/I HAVE NOT RAISED ANY ISSUES THIS YEAR [required]
- If you have answered YES or NO above, please could you explain your answer in some more detail? [optional]

Additional/Alternative Questions?

For those colleagues who do wish to include compulsory questions, e.g. if you feel your students may not respond if they are unsure what to say, it may be useful to ask primer yes/no questions such as 'Have you used the Library?' before asking students for qualitative feedback.

For those who wish to track quantitative feedback across meetings and years, you may wish to ask Likert scale questions.

Some may wish to ask questions that track National Student Survey (NSS) themes, e.g. organisation and management, how interesting students find sessions. Be aware of the rules on inappropriate influence (available on the Office for Students website) and do bear in mind that students may be put off providing SVM feedback at all if there are too many questions to answer.